

Synthesis of Azo Disperse Dyes from 2-(1',4'-Bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline

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Intensive efforts have been made in the investigation of monoazo dyes containing a heterocyclic moiety as a diazo component owing to the marked bathochromic effect of such groups compared to a corresponding benzenoid compound¹. Dyes based on aminoquinazolinone ring are unique because of their high tinctorial power and good fastness properties towards certain fabrics². These dyes have higher tinctorial power than the conventional disperse dyes in addition to the essential dyeing properties³. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise a number of azo disperse dyes based on 4-oxoquinazoline system and study their dyeing performance on nylon, polyester and cellulose triacetate fibres. The azo disperse dyes of the following structure were prepared :

Results and Discussion

Ring closure of *N*-acetylanthranilic acid afforded 2-methyl-4-oxo-3,1-benzoxazine, which was converted to 2-methyl-4-oxoquinazoline by reaction with ammonia, using the reported procedures⁴. The methyl group in 2-methyl-4-oxoquinazoline behaves as a reactive methyl group and condensation with *p*-tolualdehyde gave the styryl derivative, which on further condensation with 4-chlorobenzaldehyde gave 2-(1',4'-bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline. Reduction of this compound with sodium sulphide afforded the amino compound and this was used as the

diazo component in the synthesis of a number of azodisperse dyes (Table 1) in 70–82% yields. All the dyes were characterised by ir and pmr spectral data. The absorption spectra (DMF) of the dyes revealed λ_{\max} in the range 435–545 nm. All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND *K/S* DATA OF
2-(1',4'-BIS-STYRYL-4''-CHLORO)-6-ARYLAZO-4-
OXOQUINAZOLINES (1-9)

Compd. no.	Coupling component*	M.p. °C	<i>R_f</i>	<i>K/S</i> **
1	Naphthol-AS	273	0.85	0.66
2	Naphthol-AS D	307	0.92	0.60
3	Naphthol-AS OL	294	0.76	0.61
4	Naphthol-AS BS	316	0.72	0.65
5	Naphthol-AS E	> 320	0.93	0.56
6	Naphthol-AS BO	221	0.76	0.63
7	Naphthol-AS SW	> 320	0.78	0.61
8	Naphthol-AS G	287	0.93	0.57
9	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	275	0.79	0.58

*AS=aniline, AS D= *o*-toluidine, AS OL = *o*-anisidine, AS BS = *m*-nitroaniline, ASE = *p*-chloroaniline, ASBO = 1-naphthylamine, AS SW = 2-naphthylamine, AS G = ethylacetoacetate and *o*-toluidine.* ***K/S* value is only for dyed polyester samples.

These dyes were applied to nylon, polyester and cellulose triacetate fibres and gave yellow to brown hues (Table 2). Dyeings on nylon and polyester were deeper than those of cellulose triacetate fibre except in the case of compounds 6 and 7.

The general dye bath exhaustion was assessed by spectrophotometric evaluation of the exhaust liquors. The percentage exhaustion of the 2%

line (12.0 g, 0.039 mol) suspended in acetic anhydride (80 ml) was gradually heated to 130° affording a clear solution. *p*-Chlorobenzaldehyde (5.47 g, 0.039 mol) was added to it and the reaction mixture refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mass was then cooled, filtered, the solid washed with acetic acid and hot water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (78%), m.p. 297°.

2-(1',4'-Bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline : 2-(1',4'-Bis-styryl-4'-chloro)-6-nitro-4-oxoquinazoline (8.21 g, 0.02 mol) suspended in a solution of sodium sulphide (14.4 g, 0.06 mol) in water (75 ml) was refluxed for 2 h yielding a deep reddish brown solution. After cooling, diluting with water (75 ml) and strongly acidifying with HCl, the solution was boiled for 20 min and filtered. Addition of sodium carbonate yielded a pale yellow solid which was crystallised from ethanol, (63%), m.p. 260°.

Diazonium chloride of 2-(1',4'-bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline : 2-(1',4'-Bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (3.35 g, 0.008 mol) was diazotised in the usual manner. The resulting diazo solution was used for the subsequent coupling reaction.

Coupling diazo solution with various coupling components : The coupling component (0.008 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (45 ml) containing NaOH (10%, w/v) and anhydrous sodium acetate (3.4 g). The solution was then diluted with water (34 ml) and cooled in an ice-bath below 5°. A freshly prepared diazo solution was then added to it dropwise with stirring maintaining pH 8.0 by adding sodium carbonate solution (10%, w/v). The stirring was continued for 3 h at 0–5°. The reaction mixture was then heated to 60°, diluted with water (90 ml) and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol, (60°) and crystallised from DMF.

Application : All the dyes were applied to nylon, polyester and cellulose triacetate fibres according to the literature method⁵. The percentage exhaustion study of the dyes was performed

using the standard procedure and in DMF medium⁶. The results are given in Table 1. The *K/S* value was evaluated for only dyed polyester samples by computer colour matching system using the equation

$$K/S = (1-R)^2/2R$$

where *K* is the coefficient of absorption, *S* the coefficient of scattering and *R* the reflectance. The results are given in Table 1. Fastness to light, sublimation and acid and alkaline perspiration were assessed by the standard methods of testing (BS : 1006-1978). The rubbing fastness test was carried out by using a crockmeter (Atlas) in accordance with the AATCC-1961, and the wash fastness test, in accordance with IS : 765-1979. The results are given in Table 2.

2-(1',4'-Bis-styryl-4''-chloro)-6-aryloxy-4-oxoquinazolines revealed the following spectral bands : ν_{\max} 740–760 (C–Cl), 1 010–1040 (C–H out-of-plane deformation of *trans*-CH=CH-), 1575–1 585 (N=N), 1 625 (C=O stretch of 4-oxoquinazoline) and 3 345–3 400 cm^{-1} (NH and OH); pmr δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) of dye 2 2.19 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.9 (1H, bs, OH), 6.73 (2H, s, CH=), 7.17 (2H, s, =CH), 7.3 (2H, NH exchangeable), 6.6–7.56 (17H, m, ArH), 8.19–8.62 (3H, m, ArH of quinazoline) and dye 7 δ 5.75 (1H, bs, OH), 6.84 (2H, s, CH=), 7.05 (2H, s, =CH-), 7.3 (2H, NH exchangeable), 6.99–7.67 (2, OH, m, ArH) and 8.19–8.65 (3H, m, ArH of quinazoline).

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